

METHODS OF SPEAKING SKILLS*M. Murodullayeva*¹*Abstract:*

Speech is not writing, but rather oral communication, the primary and most basic form. People have been speaking and listening long before there was anything to read, throughout the ages. The creation of writing in the long history of humanity is a fundamental ability. This article on teaching speech skills; the basic beliefs about speech skills; how to learn and teach speech skills; various activities and tasks related to improving conversational skills; and finally, how to teach pronunciation to learners.

Key words: teaching, learning, speech, skills, fluency

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Oral communication is an important communication skill that teachers should teach their students. Learn the importance of and the different skills involved in this type of communication, and discover some methods and strategies to teach them, including conversation groups presentation and metacognition. Language is remarkable thing. There are many languages in the world, and only a few of them are spoken without a written script. Most languages use not only written scripts but also oral forms of communication such as sounds, words, expressions, and sentences. It is a fact that learning a language first through speaking is more beneficial than learning it through writing. Children naturally have the ability to listen and speak in their mother tongue. After that, they are sent to school to learn reading and writing skills. Speaking is “the process of building and sharing meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, in a variety of contexts” Speaking plays a crucial role in second language learning and teaching. Despite its importance, for many years, teaching speaking has been undervalued and English language teachers have gone on teaching speaking just as of drills or memorization of dialogues. However, today’s world requires that the goal of teaching speaking should improve students communicative skills. (said Chaney). Listening and speaking are taught and learned sequentially within the four skills. The teacher introduces the language object in the classroom and the students say it in the situation. Speaking is the best introduction to the skills of learning other language. Learning through speech is a sample way of learning a foreign language, giving the opportunity to use a foreign language in a practical way. Not brings fluency, correction and accuracy to English language teachers and allows students to use their class time more efficiently. Encourage the reverse or dry redirection technique to build communities put more than ten sentences together, organize role-plays and pair work as much as possible and control the correcting of active and passive activation of students. Each social interaction provides students

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with new opportunities to practice the language. Some of your students may need guidance on how to enter a conversation. Therefore, encourage as much interaction as possible. Ask question, repeat the students answer, and provide advice to help them improve their speech. Your students may not use perfect syntax in informal speech, but encourage them to do so as they would in the classroom. During class, make eye contact with the students and encourage them to do the same. When talking to students, ask them to identify speech difficulties they encounter and observe their voice and articulation. Good pronunciation and fluent speech skills are symbols of cultural literacy, and it is the teacher's responsibility to achieve this goal. This way, both the teacher and the student's independent efforts are required. Teachers need to teach pronunciation skills should be emphasized in the curriculum. Exams should also be tailored to the student's speaking ability. This way, students must not be able to improve their speech and pronunciation for any reason. The primary focus of this review article is on the importance of teaching speaking skills in communication classroom. It emphasizes that language is primarily spoken, not written, and that speaking is crucial aspect of effective communication. The article highlights the benefits of developing speaking skills in the classroom, as well as the challenges that teachers may face in doing so. While the classroom provides an ideal environment for improving communication skills, particularly speaking skills, teachers must be aware of the demands of today's globalized world and implement various teaching strategies to help students improve their speaking abilities. However, the article also acknowledges the potential drawbacks of teaching speaking skills in the classroom and presents relevant data to support both perspectives.

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